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CHARTER GENDER INCLUSION ACTION PLAN

CHARTER Deliverable D7.21

Grant Agreement Number: 869471

Project Acronym: CHARTER

Project title: Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity

Starting Date: 01/08/2020

Project Duration: 54 months

Project Officer: Alberto Zocchi

Project Coordinator: Bruce Forbes / LAY

Authors: CHARTER coordination team / LAY

Contributing partners: UHAM

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DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
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Summary

This document presents the Gender Inclusion Action Plan for the CHARTER project.

The purpose of the Gender Inclusion Action Plan is to address the requirements for Gender Equality in Horizon 2020. Gender is a cross-cutting issue in Horizon 2020, and is enshrined in the core documents that established Horizon 2020. The latter programme It has a number of objectives, of which some are relevant for individual projects funded under Horizon 2020, notably: (1) Promoting gender balance in research teams at all levels and (2) Integrating the gender dimension in the content of Research and Innovation (R&I).

This document addresses the relevance and applicability of the requirements for Gender Equality in Horizon 2020 to the CHARTER project, and sets out the measures to address these requirements in a Gender Inclusion Action Plan for CHARTER, as well as measures to identify and monitor the gender balance within the CHARTER project.

In addition, this document reiterates the recognition of the importance of gender and other diversity aspects in CHARTER and the research team's commitment from the planning and initial phases of the project with the aim to respect this issue and endeavour to address this as far as is applicable and practical.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Gender Inclusion Action Plan

The purpose of the Gender Inclusion Action Plan is to address the requirements for Gender Equality in Horizon 2020 and also to acknowledge the European Commission's Communication for a Reinforced European Research Area 2012.

Three objectives underpin the strategy on gender equality in Horizon 2020:

- Fostering gender balance in research teams, in order to close the gaps in the participation of women.
- Ensuring gender balance in decision-making, in order to reach the target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups and of 50% in advisory groups.
- Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content, which helps improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation.

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All these objectives are applicable to CHARTER, and it is the objective of this document to set out the approach for how they will be addressed in the project.

The CHARTER Consortium fully recognises that integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation will provide added value in terms of excellence, creativity, and performance as well as enhance the societal relevance of the knowledge and innovations produced. Overall, we believe that fostering diversity creates significant benefits for the research work and is an important part in maximizing the CHARTER impacts, having clear connections to the dissemination and exploitation of our results. Diverse, inclusive teams are stronger, and scientific progress is achieved faster by an inclusive and interactive community. In addition, there is evidence that diverse workplaces hold several competitive advantages and perform better economically.¹

1.2 Relevance of gender aspects for CHARTER and Polar research

In the last three decades, there has been a marked shift in the way gender is seen as relevant in Polar research – and in northern communities.

Polar research has long been shaped by the “heroic” and “masculine” image of exploration under adverse environmental conditions. This image is now changing, based on stronger awareness and acknowledgement of the contributions by female researchers in previous decades.^{2, 3} This shift is accompanied by more intensive inclusion of social sciences and humanities in Polar research – a field that used to be dominated by natural (environmental) sciences. The inclusion of social sciences and humanities has fostered reflexivity about contacts between researchers and local communities and of power differentials within research teams themselves.

Looking at the situation in academia and research more specifically, one can discern that in most countries and all disciplines of science, male domination has gradually given way

¹ Bharadwaj Badal, S., “The Business Benefits of Gender Diversity”, Gallup Business Journal, January 20, 2014

² Abdel Fattah, D., Dudeck, S., Friedrich, D., Habeck, J. O., Saxinger, G., Thompson, L., Mankova, P., Seag, M., Harris, C., Smieszek, G., Leidmann, S., & Thornton, A. E. (2020). Highlights from IASC and IASSA Workshop on Gender in Polar Research. *Northern Notes: Newsletter published by the International Arctic Social Sciences Association*, 53: 25-26. https://iassa.org/images/newsletters/NorthernNotes_53.pdf (accessed 24 November 2020).

³ Hoogensen Gjørnv, G. (2017). Finding gender in the Arctic: A call to intersectionality and diverse methods. In K. Latola & H. Savela (Eds.), *The interconnected Arctic – UArctic congress 2016* (pp. 293–303). Cham: Springer.

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to more equitable representation of women and men. Still there is a need for proactive recruitment policies that aim to facilitate gender equality in well-paid, senior positions.⁴

Gender-related power differentials also play out in northern communities.⁵ However, it would be short-sighted to relate such differentials simply to the North as a hostile “frontier” of resource extraction. Nor does it suffice to see their roots in assumedly traditional gender roles and division of labour in indigenous societies and so-called traditional forms of land use. Owing to state-induced policies of sedentarization, schooling, division of professional spheres and industrialization, differences between gender roles have become more flexible in some fields, but have been cemented or newly created in others. Modernization projects in all parts of the circumpolar North have contributed to the overall picture of indigenous men being predominantly occupied in land-use professions (hunting; fishing; and – highly relevant in the context of CHARTER – reindeer herding) *versus* women being predominantly occupied in the public sector. Concomitantly, the phenomenon of gender-specific migration patterns from rural settlements to towns and cities has been observed for several decades, shaping current understandings of gender, livelihoods, and well-being in northern communities.^{6, 7, 8, 9} Any study at the intersection of biodiversity and northern livelihoods must consider that causes and consequences of environmental and socio-economic change are likely to be viewed differently by individuals of different gender, age, physical ability, ethnic background, and social status.

Finally, the “heroic” and “masculine” image of Polar research still lingers on in public perception.¹⁰ Therefore, it is of essential importance to create scientific output and public outreach that explicitly illustrates that Polar research is conducted by female, male and non-binary individuals. This will entail to some degree the dismantling of the exceptional

⁴ Mapping the Maze: Getting More Women to the Top in Research – European Commission, February 2008, http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/mapping-the-maze-getting-more-women-to-the-top-in-research_en.pdf

⁵ Oddsdóttir, E. E., Sigurðsson, A. M., Swandal, S., & Árnadóttir, A. K. (2015). *Gender Equality in the Arctic – Current Realities, Future Challenges* (conference report). Ministry for Foreign Affairs, Iceland in cooperation with Icelandic Arctic Cooperation Network and the Centre for Gender Equality.

⁶ Heleniak, T. (2015). Arctic populations and migration. In J. L. Larsen & G. Fondahl (Eds.), *Arctic human development report: Regional processes and global linkages* (pp. 53–104). Copenhagen: Nordic Council of Ministers.

⁷ Kuokkanen, R. (2015). Gendered violence and politics in Indigenous communities. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 17(2), 271–288.

⁸ Povoroznyuk, O., Habeck, J. O., & Vaté, V. (2010). Introduction: On the definition, theory, and practice of gender shift in the North of Russia. *Anthropology of East Europe Review*, 28(2), 1–37.

⁹ Rozanova, M. S., & Mikheev, V. L. (2020). Rethinking Women's Empowerment: Insights from the Russian Arctic. *Social Sciences*, 9(2), 14.

¹⁰ Wråkberg, U. (2019). AE Nordenskiöld in Swedish memory: the origin and uses of Arctic heroism. *Acta Borealia*, 36(2), 166-182.

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image of field research under conditions of the Far North. Public outreach of research projects should also exemplify in which ways research teams benefit from gender and ethnic diversity.

2. Gender inclusion action commitment

During the planning and application phase of CHARTER, the dynamics and constraints mentioned in the previous section were carefully considered. We have endeavoured to achieve gender and career stage balance in the Consortium. Academic excellence of the Consortium is high and balanced, from natural to social sciences. In CHARTER, WP1, WP2 and WP5 are led by women. The project Consortium consists of 9 female and 12 male partner contact points. The current diversity within the CHARTER Consortium offers several benefits. The balanced representation of women and men in the project will help to improve scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, tools and policy options. Gender and career-stage balance is aimed at in all activities and male and female co-workers will equally share responsibilities of the project to avoid gender bias in our analyses.

Gender equality in science is a key priority of the European Commission and Gender equality concerns all parts of Horizon 2020. Making use of all talents and creating equal opportunities for men and women is not only a matter of fairness, but it is also an issue of economic efficiency. Embracing gender equality will contribute to EU competitiveness and to growth and job creation. The Project Coordinator will ensure that gender equality issues are addressed, in consultation with the social impact assessment task in WP6 and following EU guidance for Horizon 2020 projects.

Conducting research in areas inhabited by indigenous groups, the CHARTER research team is aware of the intersectional relevance of gender and indigeneity. Among the staff are female and male individuals self-identifying as Sámi, Nenets, and Komi. Among the members of the Expert Advisory Group two out of six are female, and two members self-identify as Sámi.

Certain age groups and women may be in vulnerable position in the Arctic communities. CHARTER team members are aware and knowledgeable on the gender roles, gender-specific aspirations and gender dynamics of Arctic communities. During participatory work and the conduction of interviews in the tundra and settlements for CHARTER attention will be paid to include representatives of both genders and from various age-groups. The main data will be collected from both male and female herders and other stakeholders involved with reindeer herding who can help with giving answers to the project questions.

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By examining pastoralism, CHARTER addresses the viability and gender dynamics of Arctic communities. Team members' research has shown that land use, gender roles, gender-specific aspirations, demography, and community well-being are closely intertwined.¹¹ Socio-economic changes, development of traditional livelihoods and other sources of income all bear out differentially on careers and life projects at the intersection of gender, age, and formal education in northern rural communities. The CHARTER Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) identifies the relevant public and stakeholders systematically in order to ensure marginalized groups are not ignored and in order to identify methods for improving stakeholders' interest and engagement with our research.

3. Gender Inclusion Action Plan for CHARTER

The existing degree of the research team's diversity and reflection of team members' positionality provides a sound basis for the three main objectives of the CHARTER Gender Inclusion Action Plan:

- (1) career equality,
- (2) well-balanced involvement in decision making and,
- (3) maximum awareness of gender-related dynamics in the region under study.

1ST OBJECTIVE: FOSTERING EQUALITY IN SCIENTIFIC CAREERS

The general guideline is to make use of all talents and create equal opportunities for all sexes and for other diversities and disabilities. Fairness is a matter of Human Rights and Sustainable Development Goals. However, fairness is not the sole basis of this general guideline. By fully embracing gender equality and considering diversity as a strength, this project will contribute to promoting coproduction of knowledge, and thereby to growth and job creation.

During the COVID-19 pandemic the inequity in working conditions may be increased and there may be gender-based imbalances in how well the work can be carried out and how stressful the situation may be. The project leader, WP leaders and all project members in responsible positions should be aware of this and understand the importance of flexibility because of varying remote working situations and family responsibilities.

¹¹ Vladimirova, V., & Habeck, J. O. (2018). Introduction: feminist approaches and the study of gender in Arctic social sciences. *Polar Geography*, 41(3), 145-163.

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In CHARTER we aim at following:

1.1 Recruitment

1.1.1 Transparent recruitment processes based on merit.

1.1.2 In all further procedures of recruiting new team members, as much as is reasonable, attain a female/male balance that also pays attention to different pay-roll positions. Try proactively to prevent a female bias in lower-paid positions and a male bias in higher-paid positions.

1.1.3 All participants follow non-discrimination policies in terms of gender.

1.1.4 Ensure that men and women in the same employment performing equal work will receive equal pay, unless any difference in pay can be justified.

1.1.5 Promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. Aim towards gender balance, to the extent possible, at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

1.2 Scientific communication (workshops, publications)

1.2.1 Create a conducive work environment that acknowledges the diversity of opinions and creativity that each project member contributes to the success of the research project.

1.2.2 With regard to speakers and chairs at scientific workshops, try to establish a balance between female and male, early-career and senior scientists.

1.2.3 With regard to scientific publications and authorship credits (lead and senior authorship in particular), pay attention to giving equal opportunities to female and male, early-career and senior scientists.

1.2.4. Be aware of and try to avoid possible forms of gender bias during project communications and dissemination.

2ND OBJECTIVE: ENSURING GENDER BALANCE IN PROCESSES AND BODIES OF DECISION MAKING

The CHARTER Consortium's main bodies of decision making are the Steering Committee and the leader/vice-leader positions of the individual work-packages WP1 to WP7. In addition, the project will include inputs from the Expert Advisory Group (EAG). The

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general guideline is to attain a female/male balance in these bodies, also ensuring that all members have the same opportunities to express their views.

2.1 Vice-leaders for individual work-packages should be appointed with due consideration of gender balance, also accounting for additional aspects of diversity.

2.2 Additional members or replacement members of the Steering Committee should be appointed with due consideration of gender balance, also accounting for additional aspects of diversity.

2.3 Additional members or replacement members of the Expert Advisory Group should be appointed with due consideration of gender balance, also accounting for additional aspects of diversity.

2.4 During all meetings of decision-making bodies, participants should respect the equal right of all other participants to speak and to express diverse opinions. Chairpersons in particular will take the responsibility to facilitate fair dialogue, curb maligning statements and aggressive speech whenever it may occur.

2.5 Beyond the meetings of the decision-making bodies, individuals in decision-making positions will look towards implementation of a conducive work environment as specified above under 1.2.1.

3RD OBJECTIVE: INTEGRATING THE GENDER DIMENSION INTO RESEARCH

The general guideline is to acknowledge the diverse needs and social situations of all individuals in the ways that researchers cooperate with each other and in the ways that researchers cooperate with local communities and the wider public. In addition, the gender dimension is integrated in the research as appropriate (see Sections 1.2 and 2).

3.1 Field research in general

3.1.1 Comply with the Inclusive Codes and guidelines for diversity, equity, and inclusion during fieldwork in Polar regions, provided by APECS (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists): apecs.is/career-resources/diversity-equity-inclusion.html

3.1.2 Inform the Consortium to whom to contact if there are infringements of the Code of Conduct or in cases of lacking respect and gender equality under non-fieldwork conditions, i.e. during everyday research processes.

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3.1.3 Before the first field work season, the CHARTER project office revised and adjusted for CHARTER the Code of Conduct / Bill of Rights, provided by APECS:

<https://apecs.is/diversity-equity-inclusion/field-code-of-conduct.html>

CHARTER Bill of Rights / Code of Conduct is found here:

<https://link.webropolsurveys.com/Participation/Public/adf144c2-1200-480b-ae5-f3e4188bace4?displayId=Fin2251523>

3.1.4 Project researchers are encouraged to sign the adjusted Code of Conduct / Bill of Rights, and by doing so, acknowledging these rights and will to do their best to act accordingly.

3.2. Field research in northern communities (WP3, WP6 in particular)

3.2.1 Try to include and consider the voices of those community members who find themselves in marginalized positions, be it because of their gender, because of their non-conforming gender-role behaviour or because of the intersectionality of gendered, age-related, disability-related, ethnic and socio-economic forms of disadvantage. Consider the power differentials in the statements of those who speak on behalf of their household, community, or municipality.

3.2.2 Consider the degree to which reindeer-herding households operate on (or divert from) the basis of gendered labour division and acknowledge the different spheres of skill and expertise, including voices of women and men.

3.2.3 Comply with procedures that safeguard the anonymity of voices of those individuals and groups who are vulnerable and could potentially suffer from negative social consequences when their opinions become known.

3.2.4. Pay attention to sex and gender dimensions in the research, when developing concepts and theories, formulating research questions, and collecting and analysing data.

3.3. Steering Committee Meetings and project documentation

3.3.1 The CHARTER Steering Committee should assess once per year to what extent the above guidelines have been implemented successfully.

3.3.2 Project reports (documentation) will include an assessment of the extent to which the Gender Inclusion Action Plan has been successfully implemented. If need be, such assessment may also include challenges and deviations.

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4. Assessing and reporting the gender balance in charter

For each periodic reporting, monitoring and further analysis of gender balance will be conducted and also internally reported, as laid out in the above Guideline Tasks 3.3.1 and 3.3.2. At the end of CHARTER, a report will be produced to show the status of males and females employment in the project. This report will include scientific/research productivity of women throughout this project in terms of participation of women in scientific contributions. This information, when combined with similar data from the other projects within the field of Horizon 2020, will provide valuable data in the monitoring of progress of women in scientific research.

Useful resources

<https://www.iarpcollaborations.org/teams/Diversity-Inclusion-Working-Group>

<https://www.arctictoday.com/women-of-the-arctic-is-now-a-nonprofit-focused-on-gender-issues/>

IARPC: Being a Woman in the Field: The Things No One Tells You:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G71NmoXYvWk>

Gender in Polar Research (page 25):

https://iassa.org/images/newsletters/NorthernNotes_53.pdf

Important paper to consider when discussing co-authorship-policies:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/bes2.1705>